

**The
Alan Turing
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Evidencing the Impact of Research Software Engineers on Arts & Humanities Scholarship

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Introduction to Research Software Engineers

The term Research Software Engineer (RSE) was coined during a software sustainability workshop at the University of Oxford in 2012, but the role it describes existed long before that moment.

For decades, as the potential of software to accelerate research continued to expand across numerous disciplines, a growing community of intellectually curious and obliging software engineers have been utilising their skills to create research software that is effective, efficient, and reproducible.

During that time they have enabled outputs for which there existed no formal means of receiving credit, nor opportunities for career advancement, and their erstwhile invisibility to the UK's Research Excellence Framework (REF) may have prevented potentially important research projects from securing funding.

The creation of a title for this emerging class of research professionals, and a vigorous global campaign to secure recognition, has done much to help software engineers and researchers achieve their collective potential. There is recognition across the research landscape that RSEs are essential to the operation of effective research, reflected in the fact that UKRI recently awarded £10.2 million to the Software Sustainability Institute – a leading organisation in the RSE movement – through its Digital Research programme (UKRI, 2024). This award was consistent with previous pronouncements by UKRI:

If the UK is to meet the ambition of remaining at the forefront of computational and data-intensive science, the career development of research software engineers and research data professionals is critical. (*UKRI infrastructure opportunity report*, 2023)

Arguments for greater RSE recognition and capacity have appeared in places as influential as [Nature](#) and the UK [Government's 2017 Industrial Strategy](#).

Nonetheless, there continue to be misconceptions and missed opportunities in the field, arising from a widespread presumption that software is a tool reserved for scientists and programmers.

RSEs in the Arts and Humanities

Google's recently introduced generative AI overviews are strictly experimental, but their contents can be revealing. In response to the question "what do Research Software Engineers do?", Google explains that these professionals "work closely with researchers from various *scientific* disciplines".

This is correct, but incomplete. While it is common for the term Research Software Engineer to be associated exclusively with scientific research, the need for RSEs among Arts and Humanities (A&H) researchers is just as great – not only because software can organise information and perform a range of research functions more quickly and capably than a human being, but also because software expertise tends to be less prevalent among A&H researchers than it is among researchers with backgrounds in science and technology, whose degree programmes often include coding modules.

There is now widespread recognition of the importance of RSEs in academia. Around 40 universities across the UK now employ RSE teams to assist with research projects, and there are thought to be around 10,000 RSEs worldwide (Chue Hong *et al.*, 2023).

Numerous institutions have produced evidence of their impact in the form of case studies. At Imperial College London, RSEs have assisted with a number of projects since 2018, detailed in a selection of [case studies](#) published by the RSE team. They include work on [Nektar++](#), a piece of open-source scientific software used around the world in computational fluid dynamics, and on [StrainMap](#), a safe and fast MRI technique for gathering detailed information about the heart in motion. Their work on StrainMap involved ensuring that all software was efficient, reliable, and robust, while also creating an intuitive graphical user interface for use by clinicians with no coding expertise.

The N8 Centre of Excellence in Computationally Intensive Research, meanwhile, maintains a record of case studies from universities across the north of England. These demonstrate RSE impact on a range of projects including the [Respire data dashboard for COPD](#) patients, developed at Lancaster University; reduced computation time for code originating in the University of York's Department of Mathematics; and the [SAVSNET programme](#) for collecting and analysing veterinary data, in collaboration with the University of Liverpool.

There are humanities projects among these case studies. They include [The Linguistic DNA](#) – an analysis of 1 billion words from 60,000 printed English documents of the 16th and 17th centuries, which RSEs made possible by developing a bespoke computational linguistics tool. And at Newcastle University, RSEs created a mobile app enabling members of the public to collect and submit [photographs of prehistoric rock art](#) to contribute to its conservation.

But the overwhelming weight of evidence of RSE impact is in the scientific, mathematical, and technical domains, contributing to a distorted understanding of the role and the possible frustration of its potential to drive A&H research. Advances in high-performance computing, machine learning, and AI are transforming the research landscape, and it is important that the benefits are shared among academic disciplines. RSEs are the vital link between research and the software that can unlock its potential.

To better understand the scope of the need for RSE capability in the A&H, and the impact it is already having, The Alan Turing Institute conducted a survey of academics and researchers, collecting data on the impact that RSEs have had on the quality, scalability, reliability, and reproducibility of research outputs; the scope and ambition of projects; and other areas of enquiry. A full list of relevant questions included in the survey is given below.

Category(s) of evidence

- What discipline(s) does this evidence draw on? (NB: we are using [UKRI research councils](#) as a proxy for disciplines)
- What discipline(s) does this evidence contribute to? (NB: we are using UKRI research councils as a proxy for disciplines)
- Considering this evidence, what did RSEs enable that would not have been possible otherwise?

Respondents were invited to elaborate on this answer in one of more of the following ways:

- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs delivered valuable software/data outputs?
- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs improved quality/reproducibility/reliability/scalability of research?
- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs accelerated research or enabled a more ambitious scope?
- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs enhanced engagement or presentation?
- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs delivered cross-disciplinary methods/technical innovations or other impacts?
- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs imparted skills/knowledge that others have applied independently?
- Considering this evidence, how have RSEs improved sustainability/reusability of outputs?

The survey received 26 entries, 19 of which related to research contributing to A&H – ten of those exclusively. Disciplines appearing alongside A&H included Engineering & Physical Sciences, Natural Environment, Biotechnology & Biological Sciences, Medical Research, Economic & Social Sciences, and Science & Technology facilities.

In terms of topics, A&H projects broadly fell into three categories: language, geospatial analysis, and data management. The next session is a representative overview of RSE impacts in these three areas, as reported by survey respondents. Indented quotations are anonymous and therefore unattributed.

Language

Submissions associated with language included [Language of Mechanisation](#), which is part of the Turing's Living with Machines project. The goal of this project is to understand how mechanisation changed people's lives in the 19th century, and it includes an analysis of the ways in which the meanings of mechanisation-related words changed throughout the period. Among the outcomes of this research is an [interactive analytical notebook](#) maintained by King's Digital Lab.

RSEs played a crucial role in transforming the Language of Mechanisation project from a traditional historical study into a sophisticated digital humanities initiative. [...] Their work bridged the gap between academic research questions and technical implementation, making it possible to process large-scale historical newspaper data and integrate citizen science contributions.

The [Daidalos Project](#), meanwhile, is a research infrastructure for literary studies and philology, using natural language processing to carry out sentiment analysis, the identification of entities within a text, and other functions. By automating the process of textual analysis, this tool allows researchers to conduct literary research at speed and to approach classical texts in new ways, with enormous implications for literary scholarship.

The team behind the Daidalos Project reserved significant credit for the RSEs who enabled the output.

[T]hey have a keen understanding of research methodologies, a specific subject and coding – they bridge the gap between traditional and digital research and know limits of both

cultures ... providing access to methods that would be otherwise unknown in the research field.

Geospatial analysis

RSEs have also proved invaluable in allowing historians and other humanities scholars to analyse map data at scale, as evidenced by the significant number of submissions on this theme.

[MapReader](#) is part of the Turing's Living with Machines and Data/Culture projects. An open-source tool allowing researchers to analyse map images, MapReader was created for historical research but has potential applications in other areas thanks to the input of RSEs and the standards of scalability, reproducibility, and openness to which they work.

RSEs have ensured that best practices are followed when developing the code, making it user friendly and accessible for others. [...] The code was initially developed for historians but is now being adopted by other fields, e.g. the UK National Parks are using it for conservation purposes.

There is evidence here, and in other case studies, that the input of RSEs has not only enabled research outputs and created versatile research tools, but also given A&H researchers important skills around software best practice and data management. For example,

[w]orking with RSEs has helped upskill the historians we work with by demonstrating best practices within the code [...] This knowledge can be applied more broadly and in future projects.

Or, as another respondent put it more succinctly, “[w]e got historians using Github!”

Map data was also used to support UCL's [Legacies of British Slavery](#) project. The output for this piece of work is a database of records related to slave owners and victims of slavery, largely in the Caribbean. RSEs contributed to the creation of a Maps page, which serves as an accessible entry point to the database for researchers and members of the public.

RSE contribution allowed the geospatial extension of the database; presentation of interactive maps; georeferencing of historical maps to use as background and reference for plantation locations; analysis and preliminary geolocation of existing address data.

RSEs even helped researchers to map underwater landscapes in support of Historic England's Unpath'd Waters project. Using maritime data that they themselves helped to compile and organise, RSEs allowed the researchers' work to reach a wider audience by creating

simulations and 3D models to visualize submerged landscapes and shipwrecks, making it possible for the public to explore underwater heritage sites virtually. This approach brought inaccessible parts of history to life, engaging a wider audience.

To the same end, these research specialists co-designed the Needles Voyager, a “digital platform for allowing users to explore shipwrecks and maritime sites off the Isle of Wight”.

Data management

Managing and accessing vast quantities of physical and digital data is an ever-growing challenge for A&H researchers, and on the basis of our survey this appears to be an area of research in which RSEs can have a significant and widespread impact.

The modernisation of King's Digital Lab was a year-long project in which RSEs played a crucial role in improving the sustainability and reusability of around 85 research projects. Our survey respondent was keen to emphasise that the impact of their contribution was significant not only in the short term but in the longer term too.

Without RSEs, these research projects would likely have become inaccessible or significantly degraded over time, representing a substantial loss of academic knowledge and research investment. Their work not only preserved this knowledge but also made it more secure, accessible, and sustainable for future generations of researchers.

What's more,

[t]hese improvements not only extended project lifespans beyond initial funding cycles but also reduced operational costs, with savings passed on to partners and Faculty.

RSEs also contributed significantly to the development of Heritage Connector, a software tool that automates the extraction of meaning from unstructured heritage data and allows it to be searched through an interconnected platform. This has helped not only researchers but members of the public to review previously inaccessible heritage data.

The RSE-led development of open-source APIs and data management tools has opened up new avenues for researchers and the public to explore heritage collections interactively. By linking disparate data sources and enabling dynamic updates, they have transformed static archival records into an evolving resource that supports deeper scholarly enquiry and more engaging user experiences.

RSEs had a similar impact on Our Heritage, Our Stories, a project whose aims include transforming siloed, transitory, and frequently overlooked community-generated digital content into a searchable national resource. Once again, managing this enormous quantity of widely distributed data would have been impossible without RSEs, whose input not only allowed researchers to collect and organise the material, but also to present it to the public in an accessible format.

They engineered a dynamic, interactive interface – the Observatory – that allows anyone to search, reuse, and remix this newly linked heritage data. This digital platform not only democratises access but also supports ongoing research and community engagement.

Conclusion

The results of this survey constitute the largest single body of evidence of the impact of RSEs on A&H research. This impact is felt in a range of A&H disciplines, allowing historians, philologists, archivists, anthropologists, and scholars from many other A&H subjects to organise, present, and find meaning in the vast and rapidly growing range of data available to them. The work of RSEs not only expands the scope of research, but also makes its findings digestible to a non-specialist audience.

Our respondents were universally positive on the impact of RSEs, which is to be expected given the nature of the survey. RSEs receive credit for making outputs possible, accelerating research, and even cutting costs.

But there is also evidence in these responses that RSEs and humanities researchers help each other. One respondent neatly captured the dynamics of this mutually beneficial relationship in two separate responses.

The RSE – with a totally different background from the domain of this research – was able to work extremely successfully across disciplines, and translate between machine learning and historical research with ease.

And,

[t]he RSE developed worked examples that enabled the rest of the team to use the code independently.

In other words, the RSE (we can assume) became a better historian, more able to help with future projects in this subject area, and the historian became a better coder, more able to manage and engineer software for themselves. It would be difficult to imagine a more complete example of constructive knowledge exchange between two traditionally disparate domains.

As these survey responses show, RSEs are already demonstrating their potential to accelerate and expand A&H research. Recognising the role that these technically skilled professionals play as facilitators of progress in A&H is an essential step towards capitalising on this potential.

Acknowledgements

We would like to thank all those who have contributed, under anonymity, to the evidence base (Beavan *et al.*, 2025). Without these rich responses we could not have created such a community-inspired document.

The credit framework we use is the Contributor Roles Taxonomy ([CRediT](#)) – a high-level taxonomy comprising 14 roles that can be used to describe contributions to a research output. While the contributor roles definition can be open to interpretation, we consider that they fit well the types of contributions we have attributed to the authors.

Conceptualisation, Investigation, Methodology, Project administration, Writing – review & editing: David Beavan, André Piza

Conceptualisation, Data curation, Formal analysis, Investigation, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing: Rob Hearn

Conceptualisation, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision: Pieter Francois
Data curation, Supervision: David Beavan

Conceptualisation, Project administration: Stephanie Fagan

Visualisation: André Piza, Emma Rowlands

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Survey responses

Below we have provided a collection of survey responses by question for ease of reference, omitting those that were deemed too brief or unclear to be included as standalone quotes. All responses, long or short, were gratefully received. A complete record of survey responses can be found in Evidencing the Impact of Research Software Engineers: survey database (Beavan et al., 2025).

Considering this evidence, what did RSEs enable that would not have been possible otherwise?

“Without RSEs, these research projects would likely have become inaccessible or significantly degraded over time, representing a substantial loss of academic knowledge and research investment. Their work not only preserved this knowledge but also made it more secure, accessible, and sustainable for future generations of researchers.”

“RSEs in Heritage Connector not only automated the extraction of meaning from unstructured heritage data but also created an adaptable, interconnected platform that brings previously isolated records into a unified, research-enabling ecosystem. This digital leap – made possible by their technical expertise – has fundamentally expanded what museums can offer in terms of data-driven research and public access.”

“RSEs played a crucial role in transforming the Language of Mechanisation project from a traditional historical study into a sophisticated digital humanities initiative. By developing specialised analytical notebooks, they enabled complex analysis of historical language changes across multiple dimensions - temporal, geographical, and political. Their work bridged the gap between academic research questions and technical implementation, making it possible to process large-scale historical newspaper data and integrate citizen science contributions.”

“they have a keen understanding of research methodologies, a specific subject and coding - they bridge the gap between traditional and digital research and know limits of both cultures”

“The RSEs created a user-friendly system that bridges the gap between automated and manual accessibility testing. By developing Webval, they made it possible to systematically track, annotate, and manage WCAG compliance issues in a way that would be more complex and time-consuming using traditional methods.”

“RSE contribution allowed the geospatial extension of the database; presentation of interactive maps; georeferencing of historical maps to use as background and reference for plantation locations; analysis and preliminary geolocation of existing address data. Specialist technical knowledge helped extend the database system for long-term use by the research team and accessible presentation of the geolocated data to external users.”

“In essence, without the contributions of RSEs, the rich and diverse community-generated digital content – which is a vital but previously siloed part of the UK's heritage – would

remain fragmented, hard to discover, and at risk of being lost. Their work has thus enabled a sustainable, innovative solution to preserve and reimagine our national collection.”

“We would never have been able to turn MapReader from a piece of code for a paper from a research project into an easy-to-use end-to-end pipeline for humanities researchers around the world to use without the RSE involvement in this work.”

“We would not have been able to write the code for the full end-to-end pipeline and perform an experiment at scale with 15k maps (including evaluating the output).”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs delivered valuable software/data outputs?

“The RSEs delivered valuable outputs through analytical notebooks that efficiently processed historical newspaper data and citizen science contributions. These tools supported both traditional academic publishing and computational research methods, enabling researchers to track complex language changes across multiple dimensions. The collaborative development with academics ensured the software effectively met research needs while maintaining technical quality and usability.”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs improved quality / reproducibility / reliability / scalability of research?

“The RSEs work has essentially created a more robust, reliable, and sustainable foundation for digital humanities research, ensuring that decades of research remain accessible and usable for future scholars.”

“Both RSEs made the documentation useful for maintainers as well as users, and ensured that the software makes creating data from maps an entirely reproducible process. Furthermore, the updated code was designed to enable MapReader to function in HPC environments, enhancing the scalability of the code in our current research.”

“Made quality, reproducibility, and scalability possible: none of these would have been achieved without RSE.”

“They developed integrated management tools to protect significant maritime heritage, facilitating better preservation and sustainable management of these resources.”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs accelerated research or enabled a more ambitious scope?

“We would only have pursued small-scale experiments without RSE rather than undertaking a major task producing a huge, reusable, and reproducible dataset.”

“By applying AI technologies, RSEs developed innovative methods to search across newly linked collections, enhancing the ability to discover and analyse maritime heritage data.”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs enhanced engagement or presentation?

“The RSEs’ work has improved how research is presented and accessed, ensuring that decades of digital humanities research remains engaging and accessible to both current and future audiences, while maintaining the scholarly integrity of the original projects.”

“RSEs have ensured that best practices are followed when developing the code, making it user friendly and accessible for others. We have also created extensive documentation for the code, this has helped new users get started with the code and lowered the barrier to entry. We have also been able to run workshops for people interested in using the code, in which we help them install MapReader, run through some worked examples and troubleshoot any initial issues. RSE knowledge is crucial for this.”

“They engineered a dynamic, interactive interface – the Observatory – that allows anyone to search, reuse, and remix this newly linked heritage data. This digital platform not only democratises access but also supports ongoing research and community engagement.”

“RSEs have played a central role in training researchers to use MapReader, alongside the other team members, and in writing papers to showcase Mapreader methods or apply them in specific domains.”

“The code is reusable and the RSE made a major contribution to developing worked examples and training others to use the code.”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs delivered cross-disciplinary methods/technical innovations or other impacts?

“Working with RSEs changed our very model of collaboration, and the tools and strategies we employed to enable it. We got historians using Github!”

“The RSEs have worked across the humanities and computer and geographical sciences to impact all of these fields, making computational studies of large digitised map collections possible for the first time in a way that is accessible to researchers with very little previous computational experience.”

“The RSE – with a totally different background from the domain of this research – was able to work extremely successfully across disciplines, and translate between machine learning and historical research with ease. The code reflects this.”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs imparted skills/knowledge that others have applied independently?

“A wide range of scholars are now using EFES – and developing it further in the process.”

“Working with RSEs has helped upskill the historians we work with by demonstrating best practices within the code as well as using tools like git and github. This knowledge can be applied more broadly and in future projects.”

“Non-RSEs on the team have become better coders, better at documenting, better at working in an agile fashion.”

“In MapReader workshops in the last two years, RSEs have contributed to training over 200 people to reuse this software for map analysis.”

“The RSE developed worked examples that enabled the rest of the team to use the code independently.”

Considering this evidence, how have RSEs improved sustainability/reusability of outputs?

“The RSEs improved sustainability and reusability by modernising approximately 85 research projects through containerisation and standardisation. The “static-first” approach for legacy projects reduced maintenance costs and security risks while preserving core functionality. By implementing infrastructure-as-code practices and creating reusable templates, they ensured projects could be reliably reproduced and maintained. The migration to centrally managed infrastructure, combined with automated security patching and optimised resource allocation, created a sustainable foundation. These improvements not only extended project lifespans beyond initial funding cycles but also reduced operational costs, with savings passed on to partners and Faculty.”

“The RSEs made a strategic decision to build the entire application on GitHub's infrastructure, ensuring long-term sustainability. This choice means the application runs entirely on GitHub servers, eliminating the need for dedicated hosting infrastructure and reducing maintenance overhead. The approach ensures the tool remains accessible and functional as long as GitHub exists, which is a significant consideration for long-term sustainability.”

“Both RSEs working on MapReader have improved MapReader's efficiency, ensured it is easy to maintain, and helped to develop approaches to the reuse of output data through creating a Zenodo community and publishing models on Hugging Face.”

“The code was initially written in a way that already supported reuse and was sustainable without major change for the initial first year. When another RSE joined the project, the code was easy to adapt and maintain, building on that solid foundation.”

“By creating an easy to use codebase, with version control (git) and versioning, it makes it significantly easier to reproduce and reuse outputs. MapReader datasets are created in consistent ways making them easier to compare. RSEs have also ensured best practices in storing/sharing data, e.g. via zenodo and HF. This makes it much easier to reuse in other research.”

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